

Facial Capillary Hemangioma, Nasopharyngeal Hemangioma, and Dandy Walker Malformation

Mona al-Saleh, MD;¹ Thomas M. Bosley, MD;¹ Claude Jacquemin, MD²

BACKGROUND

Brain malformations and pharyngeal hemangiomas may occur in association with facial hemangiomas.

CASE REPORT

A 75-day-old Saudi girl presented with a large facial capillary hemangioma, Dandy-Walker malformation, and nasopharyngeal angioma partially obstructing the airway.

CONCLUSION

Patients with large facial capillary hemangiomas should be carefully examined for central nervous system malformations and for vascular malformations involving the airway that might cause respiratory distress. This type of midline developmental field anomaly might be more frequent than realized.

(*MEJO 1999;7: 92-94*)

FACIAL CAPILLARY HEMANGIOMAS ARE among the most common orbital and periorcular tumors in children. They usually involute spontaneously and do not require active intervention from an ophthalmologist. On occasion, however, these benign tumors can be associated with potentially vision- and life-threatening complications.

CASE REPORT

A 75-day-old girl, product of a normal pregnancy and delivery, developed a raised, pink lesion involving the right upper lid shortly after birth. The lesion gradually increased in size over a period of days, eventually closing the right eyelid, and another lesion appeared on the right lower lid that extended gradually to the right side of the jaw (Fig. 1).

A MRI performed to assess the extent of this lesion within the orbit revealed a posterior fossa anomaly with agenesis of the cerebellar vermis, hypoplasia of the right cerebellar hemisphere, and opening of the fourth ventricle into the

basal cistern (Figs. 2, 3), an appearance diagnostic of the Dandy-Walker malformation.^{1,2} Intralesional steroid injection was planned because of the threat to vision from sensory deprivation amblyopia OD. Prior to anesthesia, another angiomatic lesion suspected on MRI (Fig 3) was observed in the subglottic region partially obstructing the airway. After transfer to a general hospital, the child underwent general anesthesia for steroid injection of the lid hemangioma. Laryngoscopy and bronchoscopy revealed subglottic and glottic hemangiomas with subglottic stenosis requiring tracheotomy. The patient was treated with prednisone 4 mg/kg/day, which resulted in marked improvement of the facial hemangioma but no change in the laryngeal hemangioma. Endoscopic steroid injection into the subglottic tumor caused some reduction in size of the mass but not enough to permit safe closure of the tracheotomy at the time of the last outpatient visit at age 18 months.

DISCUSSION

Facial capillary hemangiomas appear shortly after birth with initial rapid growth until one year of age followed by spontaneous involution that typically is complete by the age of 5-7 years.³ They may result from islands of angioblastic tissue which fail to make normal contact with the adjacent vascular system and which respond indepen-

From the ¹Neuro-Ophthalmology Division and ²Department of Radiology, King Khaled Eye Specialist Hospital, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Corresponding author: Thomas M. Bosley, MD, King Khaled Eye Specialist Hospital, PO Box 7191, Riyadh 11462, Saudi Arabia.

Figure 1. Large facial capillary hemangioma with secondary lid closure.

dently to growth factors in the postnatal period.⁴ Usually these lesions are managed conservatively, and active intervention by intralesional steroid injection, systemic steroid, radiotherapy, or surgical excision is entertained only when vision is threatened by amblyopia,⁵ airways are obstructed, or a coagulopathy occurs secondary to platelet entrapment and consumption of clotting factors.⁶ Our patient required ophthalmologic intervention because of a threat of sensory deprivation amblyopia inherent in the complete closure of the right lid by the mass. Fortunately, the pharyngeal hemangioma was discovered prior to intubation, and the child has done well with intensive treatment despite complete obstruction of the upper airway.

Facial capillary hemangiomas have been reported in association with the Dandy Walker malformation in at least 16 previous patients, six of whom had microphthalmos as well.⁷⁻¹² Pharyngeal hemangiomas were discovered in

Figure 2. Coronal T2 weighted MRI image shows right cerebellar hypoplasia and absent cerebellar vermis.

Figure 3. Sagittal T2 weighted MRI image demonstrates the subglottic mass (arrow) and agenesis of the cerebellar vermis with communication between the fourth ventricle and the cisterna magna.

four of the nine patients reviewed by Reese and colleagues.¹¹ The association of facial capillary hemangiomas with nasopharyngeal hemangiomas has been described before,¹³ and this association may be particular strong in patients who also have posterior fossa malformations.

Midline CNS developmental anomalies such as the Dandy-Walker malformation have more than a chance association with midline somatic developmental defects. Opitz introduced the concept of the midline as a developmental field (rather than only an imaginary plane) where developmental defects may include the CNS and related (e.g., the eye) or remote (e.g., larynx and pharynx) tissues.¹⁴ This concept may explain malformations in our patient affecting tissues that are not overtly related or contiguous. The concept implies that insults occurring at specific critical times during embryonic development will give rise to similar developmental outcomes. The specific patho-

genic event may not be nearly as important as the time during gestation when the insult occurs.

The developmental disturbance causing the Dandy Walker malformation is believed to act between 6 and 8 weeks of gestation,⁹ while microphthalmos probably results from faulty closure of the optic vesicle between 5 and 7 weeks of development.¹⁵ Hemangiomas likely begin as an insult to development of skin blood vessels during the third month of intrauterine life.⁴ Rebolleda et al, therefore, hypothesized that events occurring between 6 and 8 weeks of gestation could result in the combination of facial hemangiomas, CNS malformations, and eye malformations.¹² A similar hypothesis would probably apply to the triad of facial hemangioma, pharyngeal hemangioma, and Dandy-Walker malformation described in our patients. This analysis is supported by the consistently ipsilateral location of CNS, vascular^{11,16} and eye anomalies^{8,9} in previously reported patients and in our patient (right facial hemangioma and right cerebellar hemisphere hypoplasia).

Ophthalmologists should be aware of the potential presence of pharyngeal and/or laryngeal hemangiomas in patients who have facial hemangiomas and CNS anomalies because of the potential for life threatening airway obstruction. We also recommend that patients with facial capillary hemangiomas be evaluated radiologically for posterior fossa anomalies that may require intervention (e.g., ventricular shunting for hydrocephalus) or careful follow-up during development. MRI is superior to CT for this purpose because of its excellent delineation of soft tissue masses and posterior fossa structures. Both the head and neck should be imaged. This type of midline developmental field anomaly might be more frequent than realized.

1. Estroff JA, Scott MR, Benacerrat BR. Dandy-Walker variant: Prenatal sonographic features and clinical outcome. *Radiology* 1992;185:755-8.
2. Zimmerman RA, Bilaniuk LT, Jusnard D. Pediatric cerebral anomalies. In: Stark DD, Bradley WG Jr, eds. *Magnetic Resonance Imaging*. St. Louis: Mosby Year Book 1992:1046-8.
3. Jacobs AH. Vascular nevi. *Pediatr Clin North Am* 1983;30:465-81.
4. Goldberg NS, Hebert AA, Esterly NB. Sacral hemangiomas and multiple congenital abnormalities. *Arch Dermatol* 1986;122:684-7.
5. Stigmar G, Crawford JS, Ward CM, Thomson HG. Ophthalmic sequelae of infantile hemangiomas of the eyelids and orbits. *Am J Ophthalmol* 1978;85:806-13.
6. Haik BG, Karcioğlu ZA, Gordon RA, Pechous BP. Capillary hemangioma (infantile periocular hemangioma). *Surv Ophthalmol* 1994;38:399-426.
7. Atkin JF, Patil S. Apparently new oculo-cerebro-acral syndrome. *Am J Med Genet* 1984;19:585-7.
8. Deady JP, Willshaw HE. Vascular hamartomas in childhood. *Trans Ophthalmol Soc UK* 1986;105:712-6.
9. Nishimaki S, Yoda H, Seki K, Kawakami T, Akamatsu H, Iwasaki Y. A case of Dandy-Walker malformation associated with occipital meningocele, microphthalmia, and cleft palate. *Pediatr Radiol* 1990;20:608-9.
10. White WL, Mumma JV, Tomasevic JJ. Congenital oculomotor nerve palsy, cerebellar hypoplasia and facial capillary hemangioma. *Am J Ophthalmol* 1992;113:497-500.
11. Reese V, Frieden IJ, Paller AS, et al. Association of facial hemangiomas with Dandy-Walker and other posterior fossa malformations. *J Pediatr* 1993;122:379-84.
12. Rebolleda GF, Munoz FJ, Padron C. Microphthalmos, facial capillary hemangioma and Dandy-Walker malformation. *Acta Ophthalmol Scand* 1995;73:173-5.
13. Yee RD, Hepler RS. Congenital hemangiomas of the skin with orbital and subglottic hemangiomas. *Am J Ophthalmol* 1973;75:876-9.
14. Opitz JM, Gilbert EF. CNS anomalies and the midline as a "developmental field" comments. *Am J Med Genet* 1982;12:443-55.
15. Flaharty PM, Papay FA, Morales L, Anderson RL. Developmental anomalies of the orbit. In: Tasman W, ed. *Duane's Clinical Ophthalmology*. 2nd ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott, 1993:1-2.
16. White CP, Jan JE. Visual hallucinations after acute visual loss in a young child. *Dev Med Child Neurol* 1992;34:259-61.